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A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON NUTRACEUTICALS: CURRENT THERAPY FOR LIFE

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ABSTRACT

Nutraceuticals are products that have both nutritional benefits and therapeutic effects, making them highly valuable in maintaining optimal health. They play a significant role in human healthcare and have become increasingly popular in promoting health and disease reduction. They are also used as a support therapy for the prevention and treatment of various diseases, including reducing the side effects of cancer chemotherapy and radiotherapy. This review article discusses the various drug-nutraceutical interactions and elaborates on several patents on nutraceuticals in agricultural applications and various diseases, confirming the exponential growth of the nutraceuticals market value. To overcome the challenges involved in the formulation of nutraceuticals, diverse novel nano-formulation approaches have been developed. These approaches have led to micronized dietary products and other nutraceutical supplements with improved health benefits. It is important to have prior information on the various interactions between nutraceuticals and drugs to prevent any deleterious effects of nutraceutical products. The latest clinical studies on nutraceuticals that show the therapeutic action of nutraceutical bioactive molecules on various diseases have also been discussed in this review article.

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INTRODUCTION

The Greek physician Hippocrates, often known as the "father of medicines" said "Let thy food be thy medicine and the medicine be thy food" focusing on the prevention of diseases. Nutraceutical is the hybrid of 'nutrition' and 'pharmaceutical'. "Nutraceutical" is a substance that may be considered a food or part of a food that provides medical or health benefits, encompassing prevention and treatment of disease.

The concept of "nutraceutical" arose first in a survey from the U.K., Germany, and France, where diet was rated higher by the consumers, than exercise or hereditary factors to achieve good health. The term "nutraceutical" was coined from "nutrition" and "pharmaceutical" by Stephen De Felice, founder and chairman of the Foundation for Innovation in Medicine (FIM), Cranford, NJ in 1989. According to De Felice, Nutraceutical can be defined as, "a food (or a part of food) that provides medical or health benefits, including the prevention and or treatment of a disease". On the other hand, Health Canada defines nutraceutical as "a product prepared from foods, but sold in the form of pills, or powder (potions) or other medicinal forms, not usually associated with foods". Nutraceuticals are found in a variety of products emerging from (a) the food industry, (b) the herbal and dietary supplement market, (c) the pharmaceutical industry, and (d) the newly merged pharmaceutical/agribusiness/nutrition companies. It may range from isolated nutrients, herbal products, dietary supplements, and diets to genetically engineered "designer" foods and processed products such as cereals, soups, and beverages.

Nutraceuticals cover most of the therapeutic areas such as anti-arthritis, cold and cough, sleeping disorders, digestion and prevention of certain cancers, osteoporosis, blood pressure, cholesterol control, depression, and diabetes^[1,2].

In the pharmaceutical industry, it is mandatory to conduct clinical tests on animals or in vitro to verify the effects of a compound. In contrast, there was no such method in the past for verifying the effects of foods in preventing or treating diseases in the field of nutrition. However, in recent years, food composition has been scientifically tested and verified. This is due to increasing awareness among people about health-related issues and how food can directly or indirectly affect proper health and the prevention of diseases (Figure 1)^[3,4].

Nutraceuticals are products that blend both nutritional and medicinal qualities. They are designed to improve physical health, fight against daily challenges like stress, and increase longevity. Nowadays, there is more emphasis on herbs that double as both food and medicine because they are more widely accepted. Due to their dynamic action, nutraceuticals are becoming more popular than traditional medicines and health supplements. This review will examine herbs with a wide variety of therapeutic values, including immunity boosters, antidiabetic agents, anticancer drugs, antimicrobial agents, and gastroprotective agents^[4].

Fig.1: Potential roles of nutraceuticals.

Nutraceuticals are natural compounds that have therapeutic benefits. These benefits include treating cough and cold, reducing inflammation in arthritis, aiding digestion, improving sleep, treating cancer, treating depression, managing diabetes, reducing cholesterol, controlling blood pressure, and relieving pain. The research and development sector for nutraceuticals is actively working to discover how these compounds can be used in the pharmaceutical industry. Scientific standards require careful development of protocols and clinical studies that will form the foundation for consumer health, and positively impact nutraceutical companies^[5,6].

In recent years, there has been a significant increase in the awareness and use of nutraceuticals as powerful therapeutic supplements. Nutraceutical medicine is recognized as a part of Complementary and Alternative Medicine (CAM), and is now considered a new branch of CAM. Due to the combined nutritional and medicinal benefits of nutraceuticals, their popularity has increased among both the general public and healthcare providers. A recent review comprehensively discusses the use of nutraceuticals in preventive and support therapy, followed by a compiled literature on patents published on this topic^[7].

CLASSIFICATION OF NUTRACEUTICALS^[2]

Fig.2: Classification of nutraceuticals.

Inorganic mineral supplements:

E.g.: calcium, magnesium, manganese, boron, copper, zinc, phosphorous, etc.

Antioxidants:

They are found in fruits, vegetables, and fish and are used to prevent reactive oxygen species and scavenging free radicals. Examples include Vitamin E, C, A, and beta-carotene.

Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA):

These are fatty acids that contain more than one double bond, including essential fatty acids such as Omega-3 fatty acids, safflower oil, corn oil, soybean oil, and fish oil.

Probiotics:

These are living microorganisms, which when taken with or without food improve intestinal microbial balance and functioning of large intestine. Eg: Bifidobacterium, Lach, bacilli, Saccharomyces cerevisiae, etc.

Prebiotics:

These are non-digestible substances that provide beneficial effects and protection to the prebiotics from gastric acid and digestive enzymes. They also promote the growth of probiotic bacteria. Eg: Oligo fructose, Inulin, Galacto-oligosaccharides, Lactulose.

Dietary fibres:

They are two types viz:- water soluble fibres and water insoluble fibres. They are present in fruits, vegetables, grains, legumes, etc. They are used to correct constipation, bowel irregularities, haemorrhoid.

Nutraceuticals in Various Diseases

Nutraceuticals can enhance health, wellbeing, and modulate immunity to prevent and treat various diseases (Figure 2)^[8]. Below are some diseases that can be treated with the help of nutraceuticals.

Fig. 3: Nutraceuticals and Dietary Supplements in various diseases.

Nutraceuticals in Cardiovascular Diseases

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are responsible for about 30% of deaths worldwide each year. These diseases impact the blood vessels and the functioning of the heart. Nutraceuticals, which are dietary supplements, are effective in managing and preventing the risks associated with CVDs. Nutraceuticals can be categorized depending on the type of CVD they are used to treat, including arrhythmias, congestive heart failure, angina, hypertension, and hyperlipidemias. There is significant evidence to suggest that nutraceuticals can be used as a form of intervention for cardiovascular diseases. In this context, some of the nutraceuticals and dietary supplements used for the treatment and prevention of CVDs are discussed in more detail^[9,10].

Alliin and Alliin

Ischemic heart disease and atherosclerosis are medical conditions that are linked to high levels of plasma triglycerides and blood cholesterol. Garlic, commonly known as *Allium sativum*, has anti hyper-lipidemic properties that help to decrease cholesterol levels. Garlic eliminates cholesterol and its by-products from the body in large amounts through feces, and it also reduces the endogenous synthesis of cholesterol. This helps in producing a better balance between HDL and LDL cholesterol levels. Alliin and alliin are compounds present in garlic that can impact cholesterol levels, but they need to be protected from gastric acids. A study of 781 patients across thirteen placebo-controlled trials has shown that garlic supplementation has a positive effect on serum cholesterol levels. Apart from being antihyperlipidemic, garlic also has intrinsic antihypertensive properties^[11].

Omega-3Fatty Acids

Omega-3 fatty acids are a type of polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA) that are obtained from marine sources. Docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) and eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) are two crucial types of omega-3 fatty acids that play an essential role in the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases. A randomized trial called the Diet and Reinfarction Trial (DART) involving 2033 men who had experienced a myocardial infarction showed that taking fish oil supplements reduced the mortality rate by 29% over a period of two years. Consumption of fish oil resulted in a 45% decrease in unexpected deaths, a 30% reduction in cardiovascular diseases, and a 20% decrease in overall mortality. Recent clinical trials have also shown that omega-3 fatty acids can decrease the risk of cardiac arrhythmias and improve the health of patients suffering from plaque formation caused by atherosclerosis. Omega-3 fatty acids have been found to enhance the electrical stability of heart cells, extending their relative refractory period and helping to treat arrhythmias^[12].

Proteins, Peptides and Amino Acids

Hypertension is a condition that is associated with cardiovascular diseases. ACE (angiotensin-converting enzyme) inhibitors are commonly used to treat this condition, but they often cause side effects such as hypotension, elevated levels of potassium, impaired renal function, coughing, and skin rashes. However, natural ACE inhibitors can be found in casein and whey protein derived from milk. Studies on animals have shown that these milk-derived proteins have antihypertensive effects. Clinical studies have also reported a statistically significant hypotensive effect^[13].

Antioxidant Vitamins

Antioxidants are often taken as dietary supplements to prevent chronic illnesses such as cancer and cardiovascular diseases. They work by reducing the oxidation of LDL-cholesterol, which is caused by free radicals. Antioxidant vitamins are naturally present in fruits, vegetables, fish, and fixed oils. They work by preventing the formation of oxygen free radicals or by capturing them. Various studies have shown that people who consume a diet rich in antioxidants have lower risks of morbidity and mortality associated with cardiovascular diseases. Antioxidant supplements that contain vitamins C and E are effective in preventing CHD. However, supplementation with β -carotene can produce adverse effects and is not recommended. According to a study conducted on American men and women aged 25-74 years, the risk of CHD decreases with an increase in vitamin C intake. The study was conducted over a period of 10 years and included subjects who were randomized with diverse combinations of 10 nutritional supplements for over five years^[14].

Phytosterols

Phytosterols, which occur naturally in vegetable oils, seeds, nuts, grains, wood pulp, and other sources, have a similar structure to cholesterol and compete for absorption through the small intestine. Studies have demonstrated that consuming phytosterols can increase the liver's uptake of LDL, reduce blood LDL levels, and decrease cholesterol absorption. Plant sterols, derived from natural grains like soy, sunflower, and corn, can reduce LDL cholesterol levels up to 15% when consumed. Further research has shown that consuming 2-3g/day of plant sterols/stanols can reduce LDL cholesterol levels up to 20%, although individual outcomes may differ^[15].

Nutraceuticals in Cancer Chemo and Radiotherapy

Radiotherapy and chemotherapy are common treatments for cancer, but they often have severe side effects such as pain, fatigue, diarrhea, vomiting, nausea and hair loss. Moreover, some types of cancer are unresponsive to these treatments, making it difficult to improve patient survival rates. In such cases, combination therapies that include plant-based supplements can help reduce the side effects of traditional treatments and increase their effectiveness. As the nutraceutical industry continues to evolve, new supplements are being developed to meet the needs of consumers. Today, many such supplements are designed not only to promote health, but also to prevent and treat diseases^[16,17].

Curcumin (Diferuloyl-Methane) from Turmeric (Curcuma Longa)

Curcumin is a powerful nutraceutical that has been proven to be effective in the treatment of cancer. Through preclinical studies, it has been demonstrated that curcumin can inhibit the development of various types of cancer, including pancreatic, colorectal, prostate, gastric, and hepatic cancer. It has been found to suppress cancer at all stages, including angiogenesis, metastasis, and proliferation. Moreover, it is much more effective when used in conjunction with chemotherapy and radiotherapy for cancer treatment^[18,19].

Ginger

Ginger is a natural supplement that has various health benefits, including being antimutagenic, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory. It is particularly helpful in reducing the side effects of radio and chemotherapy treatments, making it an excellent radio-protector agent. Furthermore, Ginsenoside Rf and Ginseng can help decrease the amount of morphine required by cancer patients. Polysaccharides present in Ginseng can also aid in minimizing the side effects of cancer treatment therapies, thereby reducing the risk of recurrence by up to 50%^[20].

Nutraceuticals for Skin Treatment

The skin, being the largest organ of the body, protects against various microorganisms, ultraviolet radiations, and chemicals while also contributing to sensitivity. However, due to its crucial role in safeguarding the body, skin can undergo changes such as immune dysfunction, photo-aging, and inflammation, which can negatively impact human health. Nutraceuticals, such as bioactive peptides, bioactive polysaccharides, botanical extracts, carotenoids, etc., can be an effective strategy for delaying or reducing the premature aging of the skin and alleviating skin-related disorders. Several human trials have demonstrated that supplementation with these products can result in fewer signs of aging and protection against UV radiation-induced aging^[21].

Bio-Active Peptides

Bioactive peptides are short chains of amino acids that can perform important biological actions. These peptides can be found in many dietary proteins, both from plant and animal sources. Animal sources include eggs, milk, and meat proteins, while plant sources include soy, oat, pulses, canola, wheat, flaxseed, and hemp seed^[22]. Peptides that are used for cosmetic purposes are usually derived from collagen and typically serve as nutraceutical formulations because of their increased bioavailability and solubility. One such nutraceutical is VERISOL[®], which contains bioactive collagen peptide (BCP). In a controlled study, VERISOL[®] was given to subjects for 8 weeks and skin wrinkles were measured before and after the treatment. It was observed that BCP promoted a significant decrease in eye-wrinkle volume in comparison to the placebo. BCP intake also showed an increase in the content of elastin and procollagen type1 along with an increase in the fibrillin content. Thus, this treatment reduced wrinkles and has encouraging effects on skin matrix synthesis. Peptan F and Peptan P are nutraceuticals of fish origin containing collagen peptides that are used to slow aging by maintaining the moisture content within skin layers.

Another nutraceutical called Celergen[®] is based on a marine collagen peptide derived from deep-sea fish, grape skin, coenzyme Q10, and lutein. A recent study has indicated improved skin properties without the risk of oxidative damage by using Celergen[®], proving it to be a safe and effective supplement^[23].

Bio-Active Polysaccharides

Polymers made of sugar are used as both energy storage and structural components in various life forms, such as plants, fungi, animals, and prokaryotic organisms. These polymers have different combinations of monosaccharides, structures, and physicochemical properties. Glycosaminoglycans from marine sources are the most useful for nutraceutical formulations. They are composed of an unbranched repeating disaccharide unit, consisting of an amino sugar called N-acetylglucosamine or N-acetylgalactosamine, and a uronic acid called glucuronic or iduronic acid. In a human trial, ten women were treated with Imedeen[®] DermOne[®] supplements containing glycosaminoglycans, protein fractions, zinc gluconate, and vitamin C, by taking 500mg of the supplement daily for 90 days. The parameters evaluated were dryness, brittleness of hair and nails, wrinkles, and mottles. After 90 days, it was found that all of these signs had improved, and increased skin thickness and elasticity were observed^[24].

Bio-Active Botanical Extracts

The extracts are mixtures of different compounds with varying structures and origins. Polyphenols, which are natural compounds found in plants, have a variety of families and structures and are useful in preventing diseases and improving health outcomes. The concentration of active metabolites in target tissues differs based on the bioavailability of different polyphenols, and the most abundant polyphenols in our diet contain the highest concentration of active metabolites. The composition and proportion of polyphenols in extracts vary depending on the extraction procedure and family. Pycnogenol[®] is a formulation made with polyphenols, rich in catechins, flavonoids, procyanidins (B1, B2, B3, B7 C1 and C2), and phenolic acids such as ferulic acid and caffeic acid. It is known for its cholesterol-lowering and cardiovascular benefits due to its antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties^[25,26].

Carotenoids

Carotenoids are naturally occurring pigments found in algae, photo-synthetic bacteria, and various plants. They have a linear tetra terpenoid structure and can be found in natural sources such as fruits and vegetables. The most commonly used dietary carotenoids include α -carotene, β -carotene, β -cryptoxanthin, lutein, zeaxanthin, and lycopene. These carotenoids are known for their benefits in skin health, such as anti-aging and photo-protection. Probiotics and carotenoids have been reported to decrease skin damage due to UV-exposure and modulate early skin biomarkers of UV effects. A carotenoid mixture supplement of α -carotene, β -carotene, and lutein has been proven effective in photo-protection. Similarly, a mixture of beta-carotene, lutein, and lycopene carotenoids is reported to protect against erythema. Vitamin C and E are also studied for their photoprotective effect and found to be effective in skin health care. Vitamin C is a hydrophilic vitamin commonly taken in large doses via consuming various food products with the intent of inhibiting the formation of carcinogenic nitrous metabolites. It acts as a cofactor for the synthesis of collagen fibers and inhibits the biosynthesis of elastin in fibroblasts, thereby preventing its accumulation, which is highly present in photo-damaged skin. In combination with vitamin E, it acts synergistically working with its mechanism of transformation. Vitamin E is the main lipophilic antioxidant and is found in the form of tocopherols. It binds with peroxy radicals, thereby preventing lipid peroxidation of polyunsaturated fatty acids. Additionally, its use for preventing photodamage, sunburn, atopic dermatitis, etc., is clearly evidenced^[27,28].

Nutraceuticals as Specialized Medical Products

It is important to note that dietary foods and enhancements that serve a specific medical purpose are considered specialized medical products. Regulatory agencies such as the European Food Safety Authority and the U.S. Food and Drug Administration, as well as national protocols issued by the Ministry of Agriculture and/or Ministry of Health in different countries around the globe, should regulate these dietary supplements.

Nutraceuticals are biological therapies that are not specific and can be used to promote wellness, prevent malignant processes, and control symptoms. The role of nutraceuticals in health promotion and disease prevention is illustrated in Figure 3. Table 2 lists various nutraceuticals that can promote health^[29, 30, 31].

Fig 4: Role of nutraceuticals in disease prevention and health promotion.

Table 1: List of nutraceuticals with health benefits^[32].

Nutraceuticals/Dietary Supplements	Nutrients	Health Benefits
Water Soluble Vitamins	Vitamin C	Wound healing, Antioxidant
	Vitamin B1	Carbohydrate metabolism, Neurological function.
	Vitamin B2	Energy metabolism, Nerve function.
	Vitamin B3	Brain function
	Vitamin B12	Metabolism of fat, protein, and carbohydrate.
Fat Soluble Vitamins	Vitamin A	Cancer, Skin disorder, Healthy vision, Antioxidant.
	Vitamin D	Absorption of calcium, Formation of bones and teeth.
	Vitamin E	Boost immune system, Antioxidant.
	Vitamin K	Blood Clotting

Formulations and Challenges Involved

Developing a high-quality nutraceutical formulation is a challenging task. It needs to be physically and chemically stable, safe, technologically feasible, and cost-effective. Unlike well-defined chemical drug molecules, botanical ingredients are complex compounds consisting of multiple chemical constituents. Often, several classes of compounds are present in a single product. Botanicals easily degrade due to heat, light, oxygen, alkaline pH, and high humidity. They also tend to have poor flow, bulk density, and variable particle size distribution. Therefore, to successfully develop a nutraceutical formulation, it's crucial to understand the physicochemical properties of different types of ingredients, use appropriate manufacturing techniques, select the right excipients, and add suitable manufacturing overages based on critical stability studies^[33,34]. In this regard, the challenges associated with different dosage forms, strategies to overcome formulation challenges, and proper selection of excipients are crucial factors to consider.

Challenges in the Formulation of Nutraceuticals and Dietary Supplement

Formulating nutraceuticals presents various challenges due to the poor aqueous solubility, high melting point, and chemical instability of active constituents. For example, omega-3 fatty acids, carotenoids, oil-soluble vitamins, and curcumin are all highly nutritious but have low solubility. Additionally, phytosterols, fatty alcohols, and carotenoids have high melting points, which can lead to instability in the formulation. Therefore, one possible solution is to prepare a solid dispersion or dissolve the nutraceutical in a suitable solvent and introduce it into food as suspended nanocrystals.

Chemical instability is another challenge for nutraceuticals. For instance, omega-3 fatty acid-rich oils such as fish oils, flaxseed oil, cod liver oils, carotenoids, lycopene, or curcumin all have stability issues. The degree of chemical degradation depends on the composition of the bioactive product, environmental conditions such as temperature, pH, pressure, presence of metals, or other oxidation-promoting agents. To protect such compounds from degradation, the development of nanoscale products is crucial. In the development of probiotics, special selective bacterial strains are necessary. In addition to these challenges, solid dosage formulation and process design for drug products and nutrition products that are alike, but the purpose and regulatory requirements may differ.

Finally, there is a challenge in formulating nutraceuticals and dietary supplement dosage forms suitable for different age groups, especially older adults and children, due to their limitations in swallowing solid dosage forms (tablets or capsules).

Therefore, advanced dosage forms such as orodispersible tablets, fast-dissolving films, and easy-swallowing gels, which are typically used in pharmaceutical applications, must be considered for nutraceutical and dietary supplement administration^[35,36,37].

Approaches to Deal with Formulation Challenges

Many nutraceuticals are made by isolating or concentrating natural sources. This is because some herbal supplements require a large dose and contain multiple active ingredients from different sources that need to be combined. Additionally, there are challenges related to compression, flow characteristics, heat and moisture sensitivity, and stability. There are different extraction processes such as microwave-assisted extraction, counter current extraction, maceration, percolation, and Soxhlet extraction. Natural bioactive compounds can come from plant extracts, herbal concentrates, fruit, vegetable, and specialty concentrates, as well as fungal and microbial materials. Excipients are often included in production, such as spray-dried carriers.

Another approach involves modifying delivery systems. Novel Drug Delivery Systems can alter the properties of compounds to create new generations of drugs and supplements. Nano-formulations, which use nanotechnology to create supplements, have been found to increase bioavailability, reduce side effects, and protect active ingredients from degradation. Polyphenols are a type of nutraceutical that has been proven to be beneficial for treating various diseases. However, they have lower bioavailability due to poor gastrointestinal absorption, hydrophobicity, and being present in polymeric or glycosylated form in foods. To overcome these challenges, researchers are exploring food processing-based techniques, nano-formulations, enzymatic treatments, probiotic combination therapies, and more^[38,39].

Liposomes and Nanoemulsions

Liposomes and Nanoemulsions are two types of bilayer phospholipid vesicles with great potential in the nutraceutical industry. They can encapsulate both hydrophilic and lipophilic materials simultaneously, leading to a synergistic effect. Additionally, they can protect sensitive bioactive compounds, enhance bioavailability, ensure sustainable release, and improve storage stability. Nanoliposomes have unique properties that make them effective in disease prevention and health promotion. For instance, nanophytosomes are a type of lipid-based nanocarrier that can deliver botanical nutraceuticals. They can be used in various food products to design novel functional beverages and foods. A study revealed that rutin complexes in the form of phytosomes exhibited increased chemical and physical stability. These phytosome complexes of rutin were formed with the help of phosphatidylcholine (PC) with a molar ratio of (rutin: PC) being (1:3) and with a particle size of less than one hundred nm and 99% encapsulation efficiency. The phytosomes masked the undesirable properties of rutin, making it a useful nutraceutical complex^[40].

Lipid-Based Carriers

Lipid formulations, such as nanocapsules and micronized carriers, can improve the controlled release, solubility, and bioavailability of phenolic compounds. For instance, β -Car nanocapsules are larger than 300 nm, and they remain physically stable even during storage, with only negligible variations. Therefore, they are suitable for use as functional foods and beverages, as well as nutraceutical products^[40,41].

Polysaccharide Matrices

These matrices are designed to degrade at specific points in the large and small intestines due to enzymatic exposure. When used as a coating for nanoparticles, they can delay the release of bioactive components until the coating is exposed in the intended environment. This property allows these coated nanoparticles to potentially target different organs in the gastrointestinal tract, thereby enhancing oral bioavailability^[40].

Excipient Selection

When it comes to creating nutraceuticals, the best approach is to adjust the formulation parameters by selecting the right excipients. The final formula must be strong enough to handle the varying physical characteristics of natural ingredients within a complex nutritional formula. Both the materials and manufacturer must meet the internal requirements for quality, safety, and performance. The effectiveness of one formulation might lead to the ineffectiveness of another. The effectiveness of excipients can only be accurately measured within the context of a specific formulation and manufacturing process. In natural product formulation, the effectiveness of excipients in a particular formula is heavily influenced by the complex combination of multiple active ingredient characteristics. Sometimes, seemingly equivalent excipients might not have the same effectiveness^[42].

Safety and Quality Control of Nutraceuticals

Nutraceuticals are supplements that can be bought over the counter, but their safety is a major concern. The most common issues are contamination, intentional or unintentional adulteration, and misleading labels. To detect adulteration, three strategies can be employed: detecting the presence of an undeclared substance, identifying a deviation from the normal content level, and recognizing an unlikely profile^[43]. Adulteration can happen unintentionally during plant growth, nutraceutical manufacturing, or storage. Contamination with fertilizers, heavy metals, microbial agents, or dust can also occur. Adulteration can also be intentional with synthetic drugs, substitute species, pollens, insects, fungi, mold, toxins, and heavy metals. Any of these contaminants can cause infections or serious illnesses such as gastritis, liver injury, and life-threatening conditions. Therefore, the quality control of raw materials and finished products is necessary and can be determined by following certain specifications outlined in monographs, along with active compound(s) stability and microbiological control.

It is crucial to note that intentional adulteration in supplements or herbal remedies can have serious harmful effects. Therefore, quality control of raw materials and finished products is necessary to prevent contamination and ensure safety. The presence of any of the contaminants mentioned above can cause infections or serious illnesses. The safety of nutraceuticals should always be of utmost importance^[44,45].

Here are some examples of adulterations to be aware of:

Ibutramine hydrochloride monohydrate is a drug molecule commonly used as an anti-obesity drug by inhibiting serotonergic and noradrenergic reuptake, and it is a frequent adulterant. In a study conducted in China using twenty-two samples of dietary supplements, eleven were found to be contaminated with phenolphthalein, N-mono-desmethyl sibutramine, and sibutramine. In another similar study performed on fifteen samples in China, four of them contained sibutramine and N-di-desmethyl sibutramine. Additionally, two pregnant women in Turkey lost their wombs due to the consumption of adulterated Chinese herbal medicine called "meizitanc". Sibutramine has also been reported as a solvent in slimming preparations and has led to mania-like psychosis in two women in Hong Kong^[46].

(b) Fenfluramine was used as an adulterant in Chinese traditional medicines and slimming preparations. It caused pulmonary hypertension and valvular heart disease and was withdrawn in 1997^[47].

(c) In some weight control programs that use appetite suppressants, diuretics, stimulants, and laxatives, the products may contain harmful ingredients such as ephedrine, norephedrine, caffeine, and furosemide^[48].

Formulation Challenges

Drug interactions happen when the effectiveness of one medication is impacted by the presence of other substances. These interactions can be classified as food-drug interactions or drug-drug interactions. Depending on the specific interaction, the pharmacological response may be changed, leading to reduced, increased, or new side effects^[49].

(a) Garlic is known for its health benefits due to the presence of alicin in it. These benefits include having hypotensive and hypocholesterolemic effects, as well as anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, and anti-fungal properties. However, it is important to note that garlic can increase the risk of bleeding when taken with anticoagulants like warfarin. It can also cause a drop in blood sugar levels when taken with hypoglycemic drugs such as insulin or glipizide. Furthermore, garlic may reduce the effectiveness of protease inhibitors like indinavir or saquinavir by lowering their blood levels^[50].

(b) Ginger is a natural remedy that is commonly used to treat various types of stomach problems, including gas, motion sickness, diarrhea, nausea, and loss of appetite. It is also used to relieve pain caused by arthritis, menstrual pain, coughs, bronchitis, and upper respiratory tract infections. However, it's important to note that taking ginger along with anticoagulant medications may increase the risk of bleeding. Similarly, if ingested with hypoglycemic drugs like insulin or glipizide, it may lead to hypoglycemia. Finally, when co-administered with calcium channel blockers, ginger may cause an irregular heartbeat or reduce its effectiveness^[51].

(c) Green tea is known to improve mental alertness and cognitive function, as it contains polyphenols. It is also used to treat a variety of medical conditions, such as Crohn's disease, Parkinson's disease, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, hypotension, chronic fatigue syndrome (CFS), kidney stones, tooth decay, and skin conditions. However, it is important to note that consuming green tea along with stimulant medications can lead to dangerous consequences, such as increased heart rate and blood pressure. It is also possible that the effectiveness of Bortezomib (Velcade) against certain cancers may be reduced if consumed with green tea. Lastly, individuals who are taking warfarin should be cautious about consuming green tea, as it may reduce the medication's effectiveness^[51].

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PROSPECTS

Nutraceuticals are a rapidly growing sector that combines medical treatment and nutrition to provide integrated medical assistance. They act as potential dietary supplements that help prevent diseases such as heart disease, support and treat various types of cancer, and provide other healthcare benefits. As a result, nutraceutical industries have come to understand and appreciate the potential success of nutrients that affect people's health.

Currently, medical care is considered to be the domain of drugs while nutrition is only regarded as a product for healthy living. However, in the coming years, it is expected that they will both interact and complement each other. The implementation of newer technologies, such as genetically modified technology in the food industry, nanotechnology-based nutraceuticals, and others, will lead to better medical treatment and healthcare benefits, which will further increase the nutraceuticals revenue market.

Scientific research has confirmed that the enhanced safety and potential benefits of newly developed nutraceutical products will encourage more investments in newer technologies. These may include nutrigenomics, converging techniques, varied imaging technologies, and their applications in nutrition development and healthcare.

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